
Jammu and Kashmir National Conference ideology, social base, role and electoral performance

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ABSTRACT

Ideology means an openly confident philosophy which formulates the basis of a social, economic and political system and for the intellectual capacity of which a promise is made, a programme framed and a mutual action taken. The programs and ideology of the National Conference aimed at all-sided expansion beside all opportunities of human activity delimited in a democratic routine on a country wide scale covering agriculture, industry, transport, tourism, handicraft, and public services.

Introduction

National Conference is the first historic region-based political party of Jammu and Kashmir State and it plays a very significant role in the political affairs of the state. The establishment of the Jammu and Kashmir National Conference found back to the pre-independence eras of Dogra ruler. The existing

National Conference was born early in the form of Jammu and Kashmir Muslim Conference party by the Sheikh Abdullah and Choudhary Ghulam Abbas in 1931. In this concern it was restricted merely to the Kashmir region still, in the 1938 the party group at that time take decision to open the doors of the party has long-drawn-out to all regions of the Jammu and Kashmir State. By means of this extension lead nature, its name was also changed from Muslim conference to all Jammu and Kashmir National Conference (AJKNC). The National Conference party sustained the accession of Jammu and Kashmir state with the union of India in 1947. It ruled the political power of the Jammu and Kashmir state since 1947 to 2015 with several breakdowns by the People's Democratic Party and Congress Party in one system or another method. Its foremost political agenda is the Kashmir autonomy. The most important achievements of the National Conference are formulation of separate constitution of the state of Jammu and Kashmir and putting into practice of land reforms. National Conference is the single state political party in Jammu and Kashmir whose Chief Minister was entitled the prime-minister of the state. Later on, similar to the other Indian states this top position was also well-known as the chief ministerial post. Since 1947, the Party National Conference was ruled in State (J&K) in one form or another till 2002, and yet again between 2009 and 2015 and again in 2024. It carries out land developments in the state, guaranteed the state's autonomy under the special Status (article 370) of the Indian constitution, and in 1957 the National Conference framed its own separate Jammu and Kashmir constitution. Farooq Abdullah from 1981-2002 and his son Omar Abdullah from 2002-2009, present respectively.

Ideology, Social Base and Role of National

The following are the programmers and ideology of the National Conference in Jammu and Kashmir state: Faith in Democracy, Secularism, Socialism, and State Autonomy, Strong Supporter of Special Status Article 370, Unity of the State, Economic upliftment, Employment programs, Rehabilitation of Kashmiri Pandits. In fact the establishment of the National Conference was positioned on secular ideology. The party at the duration of its foundation in 1938 was thrown open to any person on the circumstance that he would take oath, proclaiming that he will keep up the unity and integrity among diverse classes of the people and compromise every reasonable sacrifice for the fulfillment of freedom and an accountable and responsible government in the Jammu and Kashmir. The 2002 Legislative Assembly elections had shown a major change in the party system politics of Jammu and Kashmir. The major part of this change was the development of another regional political party of Kashmir that

challenged the dominant character of the National Conference and made the democratic space in valley highly competitive. The National Conference that had been dominating the electoral system and clean up the succeeding elections later 1977 could not continue its attractive route. Even though it quietly rises as the major party of the Jammu and Kashmir state as well as of Kashmir region, but, National Conference could not manage majority of seats in the Legislature.

National Conference ruled the Jammu and Kashmir state in coalition government with the Congress in the duration of 2008 to 2014 for complete term. But, in 2014 state legislative assembly and parliamentary elections the National Conference party's political fate throws you more over by various political dynamics. The dissimilarities over issues of removal of Armed Force Special Right Act (AFSPA), Separatist politics, demilitarization, and several further contentious subjects became highly evidences for the duration of National Conference and Congress coalition government. The twofold control over the government between Congress and National Conference contended into irregular conditions that made completely policy paralysis in the Jammu and Kashmir. That caused loss of people's faith in Congress in Jammu and National Conference in the Kashmir region. The National Conference lost its regional attractiveness by its ideologies and policies, predominantly the shattered promises over the issue of greater state autonomy by Central government by means of its leadership. The aggression of National Conference and its leaders in the direction of the development an alternate political conflict force created a sense of despotism of dominant political leadership in the political affairs of Jammu and Kashmir. It not permitted to flourish the philosophy of democratic ideas and principles. The presence of any democratic form of opposition, that moreover in a conflict torn state of Jammu and Kashmir, had several effects on the state institutions. The political phenomenon is briefly analysed by noted a Political analyst Balraj Puri as:

“Let the State's citizens enjoy as much self-esteem and confidence as those in the respite of the country. They should have the equal rights, in choosing, opposing and changing the Government at the state as are set aside decided by people somewhere else. The governing Political party in the Jammu and Kashmir state had better to enjoy as an abundant autonomy as those in other States of Indian Union in Political relations with government of majority Party in power at the union level and also with regional parties and other national to its loss of dominance in the Jammu and Kashmir state politics.

It was an unreliable result in 2002 Legislative Assembly election, moreover the three large parties including the Congress, National Conference (NC) and People's Democratic Party (PDP), there was

existence of a few number of other parties comprising the Panthers Party, Bharatiya Janata Party and the Communist Party of India (Marxist). The end of the hegemony of a single party dominance managed to the new arrangements not only of polling result but also sharing of power. All the elections since 2002, have thrown an irregular finding which has had its effects for balance of regional power. Regional disparity that was a replication of the politics of party system the pre-2002 period predominantly due to the hegemonic mechanism to control over the electoral space of Kashmir region in the influences of single party now gave way to uniformity between the regions. Since the electoral result in Kashmir region change to be split between two or more political parties, there ongoing the development of coalition governance, by means of an alliance of a Kashmir based regional party witnessed a party grounded in Jammu region.² However, it is also a fact that in the later 2002 politics of state, National Conference knew this truth that the links among the party and the people had been badly affected particularly its own political constituency. It was this polling constituency that was occupied by Bharatiya Janata Party and Congress, Panther's Party and few other political parties in Jammu, People's Democratic Party in the Kashmir. National Conference generated an electoral atmosphere wherever it was assured to recover its acceptability to seizure power by speaking diverse political concerns witness Kashmir. In this way, Jammu and Kashmir electoral politics, to some extent, became exciting and more competitive. It is in this circumstance at what time National Conference emerged as strong contestant in assembly election in later 2002 that enforced the party to reconsider its policies and programme. To keep on the opposition was possibly also favourable for National Conference, because it not merely democratized the politics of the state; however it prescribed National Conference to assume itself in the shifting political perspectives and position. It is possibly because of the development of competitive politics in the state that has forced National Conference to take up the problems of governance, and development in the respective state.

Electoral Performance of NC (2002-2024)

National Conference has been kept on a dominant force in the political affairs and electoral set-up of Jammu and Kashmir prior to the 2002 Assembly elections. But in 2002 Legislative Assembly election, it secured only 28 seats and National Conference lost its character of hegemonic dominance to the People's Democratic Party, which established the coalition government witness Congress Party. In the Assembly elections of 2008 held in the Jammu and Kashmir, National Conference gain 28 seats and

formed the coalition government in collaboration with Congress party which gain 17 seats. In the 2009 Parliamentary Lok-Sabha electoral verdict, National Conference obtains 3 seats. In the 2014 National Conference managed to secure only 15 seats and carry out the responsibilities of opposition. In 2024 Lok Sabha election National conference obtain 2 seats and in recent after 6 year presidential rule in Jammu and Kashmir Assembly election were held in Sept 2024 in three phases, National Conference got 42 seat and form Government in Jammu and Kashmir, Omar Abdullah become Chief Minister. Thus National Conference has always subjugated political scenario of Jammu and Kashmir State. National Conference has also its prodigious role in the union government whether it was United Province Alliance UPA or National Democratic Alliance (NDA). It has its important position in both state government and Central government.

Conclusion

Thus from the above study we can say that mainstream political leadership since 2002 have played significant role in democratizing the Jammu and Kashmir state institutions by representing the dissimilar political beliefs both inside and outside the state Legislative Assembly. However at the same time the advent of numerous performers have compact the power of regional Parties to bargain-basement from the Centre over the furthest crucial issue, „Self-Rule“ and „Autonomy“. Even though the political position of mainstream regional Political Parties in power to dialogue on issues of removal of Armed Force Special Power Act, talks with Hurriyat and Pakistan, Human Right Violation and release of political detainees. After getting clear-cut majority in 2024 Assembly election National Conference formed government and passed resolution in Assembly for restoration Special status of Jammu and Kashmir.

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